

One drop at a time

Recent heavy rain has led to flooding in Pakistan, devastating agricultural land, and rural communities

Thakur Prasad Tiwari¹, Naeela Qureshi², Kai Sonder², Urs Schulthess³, Alison Bentley^{2*}

¹International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), Islamabad, Pakistan

²International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), Texcoco, Mexico

³CIMMYT-China Collaborative Innovation Center, Henan Agricultural University, Zhengzhou, PR China

*Contact: a.bentley@cgiar.org

Heavy summer rains have led to severe floods in Pakistan, affecting over 800,000 hectares of land. Rural areas in the southern coastal provinces have been hardest hit with water levels remaining high throughout the Indus River system. This compounds the existing inequalities in livelihoods and represents significant humanitarian as well as agricultural impacts. Due to flood damage, the estimated direct crop loss by economists stands at around \$2.3 billion. Reports indicate that over 32 million people have been displaced by the flooding and urgent humanitarian needs include access to food, water, shelter, and public health.

Flooding affects current season crop production, revenue, and investment decisions

The current flooding has caused major damage to rice crops due to be harvested in October of 2022. Approximately half of this rice is destined for export, with Pakistan being the fourth largest exporter of fine-grained rice, predominantly selling to China, South East Asia, East Africa and the Gulf states. Although a major price shock in the global rice market is unlikely given the current high levels of global rice stocks, the rice production deficit will impact farm, household, community, and export revenue. The floods have also seriously impacted the production of cotton and sugarcane which are grown across large areas in southern Pakistan. A recent report (Qamer *et al.* 2022) summarizes the crop losses in Sindh Province (based on satellite data) which accounts for a large proportion of Pakistani rice, cotton, and sugarcane production, reporting projected economic losses totaling \$1.3 billion.

At the household level, reduced incomes are likely to influence finance available to purchase new wheat seed for the coming season, and the necessary inputs to optimize production (amplified by rising fuel and fertilizer costs). Seed availability will be a serious issue because much of the existing farm saved seed has either been washed away or damaged in storage (almost 80% of the wheat area in Pakistan is planted using farm saved seeds).

Reduced investment in the 2022-23 wheat crop is likely to impact overall productivity, exacerbating import dependency and the effects of rising import costs. Yield increases are linked to seed replacement rates and the adoption of improved cultivars. The current rate of wheat seed replacement in Pakistan is just over 20%, meaning less than one quarter of farmers replace their seed each year. Current work aims to build a stronger wheat seed system in Pakistan, supporting the adoption and replacement of improved cultivars with superior performance. Progress however is likely to be affected by limited household and community budgets, and seed system interventions are strongly encouraged.

Export revenues from rice exports also contribute to the fiscal status of the country. From a human nutrition perspective, the ability to import fruits and vegetables contributing to affordable dietary

diversity is important. In Pakistan, malnutrition and stunting are more prevalent in rural areas and targeted interventions are required to ensure access to staple crops, as well as to affordable sources of others nutritional components.

Measures needed to ensure forward wheat production

Wheat is the primary cereal staple in Pakistan with foods derived from wheat flour the main source of dietary calories for Pakistan's populations of 225 million people. Over 28 million tonnes of flour are consumed annually, and domestic demand is growing. In 2022-23 Pakistan imported 2.5 million tonnes of wheat (USDA, 2022). Prior to 2020, Pakistan was a wheat exporter, but the recent reliance on imports (in 2020 and 2021; USDA, 2022) represent an additional vulnerability to grain reserves underpinning food security, and fiscal status (particularly relevant in the face of declining gross domestic product and record high inflation). Wheat is produced on over 9 million hectares, yielding over 25 million tonnes of grain (5-year average 2017/18 to 2021/22; USDA, 2022). Wheat crops are due to be planted from late October to mid-early November, and the current flooding and high water levels need to recede in order for wheat planting to progress. Large areas of Pakistan's wheat area are currently flooded, as below.

Current areas of cropland and flood-affected crop land in Pakistan. This highlights the significant impacts of the flood waters, particularly on cropland in southern parts of the country. The boundaries shown on this map do not imply official endorsement or acceptance.

Many challenges remain to ensuring upcoming wheat planting as well as to ensuring sufficient investment in the 2022-23 wheat crop from late October to early and mid-November. More monsoon rains are expected, and flood defenses are already challenged by the volumes of water that has entered the water system to date. As we have recently highlighted in other parts of the world (Poole *et al.* 2022), investment in water infrastructure, in this case around Manchor Lake, one of the largest freshwater lakes in Asia, is urgently needed. Soil management, fertility and health must also continue to be a focus in ensuring future wheat productivity, particularly given the susceptibility of many soils in Pakistan's arable land area to erosion.

Taking stock of compounding crop production challenges

The writer and philosopher John Ruskin said "no individual rain drop ever considers itself responsible for the flood". The world is currently experiencing the impact of many coinciding threats to the stability of

our food and agricultural systems: including but not limited to the impacts on global cereal markets caused by the Ukraine-Russia war (Bentley, 2022), growing climatic instability and spiraling input and labor costs.

This is exemplified in Pakistan, where the current heavy rain and floods follow extreme heat at the end of last season's wheat cycle which reduced yields in parts of the country (<https://www.cimmyt.org/news/wheat-versus-heat/>) and compound record high levels of inflation. Extreme climatic events including heat waves and floods are growing in frequency around the world, representing significant challenges amplifying geo-political effects.

We have previously highlighted the need for greater sustained and strategic investment across the international agricultural research and development community (Bentley *et al.* 2022) to avoid the compounding of effects, and the negative fiscal loops that they create across scales from household to government level. This is urgently needed, and in the case of the current events in Pakistan, we highlight the necessity to pay close attention to the planting conditions for wheat in the coming season to ensure local, regional, and global supply can be accurately forecast.

We also strongly encourage enhanced investment in ensuring that our agricultural systems can adapt to as well as mitigate climate change impacts. In the current context, the development and distribution of improved wheat seed must be seen as a central pillar of flood response to secure wheat-dependent livelihoods. No single drop, be it geo-political or climatic, will tip the balance on our global food system. But we must be increasingly aware of the compounding and amplifying effects of each crisis and develop strategies towards more sustainable agri-food systems.

References

Bentley A (2022) Broken bread – avert global wheat crisis due to invasion of Ukraine. *Nature* <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00789-x>

Bentley A, Joshi AK, Krishna VV, Tiwari TP, Schulthess UC (2022) Wheat vs. heat <https://www.cimmyt.org/news/wheat-versus-heat/>

Bentley AR, Donovan J, Sonder K, Baudron F, Lewis JM, Voss R, Rutsaert P, Poole N, Kamoun S, Saunders DGO, Hodson D, Hughes DP, Negra C, Ibba MI, Snapp S, Sida TS, Jaleta M, Tesfaye K, Becker-Reshef I, Govaerts B (2022) Near- to long-term measures to stabilize global wheat supplies, and food security. *Nature Food* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-022-00559-y>

Poole N, Sharma R, Nemat OA, Trenchard R, Scanlon A, Davy C, Ataei N, Donovan J, Bentley AR (2022) Sowing the wheat seeds of Afghanistan's future. *Plants, People, Planet* <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp3.10277>

Qamer FM, Ahmad B, Abbas S, Hussain A, Salman A, Muhammad S, Nawaz M, Shresthra S, Iqbal B, Thapa S (2022) The 2022 Pakistan floods: assessment of crop losses in Sindh Province using satellite data. *International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development* <https://doi.org/10.53055/ICIMOD.1015>

USDA (2022) Foreign Agricultural Service <https://gain.fas.usda.gov/>